

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Vaidehi, a variety for rainfed lowland conditions in Bihar, India

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Nearly 2.2 million ha of rainfed lowland rice is grown in Bihar during kharif (monsoon) season from Jun to Dec. Late onset of the monsoon can delay transplanting. The crop may also experience flooding or drought at various growth stages. Traditional cultivars are dominant in Bihar because of their superior adaptation to abiotic stresses, including low temperature at flowering. Especially in dry years, they are susceptible to bacterial blight (BB) and brown spot (BS).

We collected diverse germplasm and evaluated it in state multilocal variety trials for 7 yr to identify a suitable cultivar for release. On average, cultivar TCA48 outperformed check cultivars Mahsuri and Br. 8 in 20 environments (Table 1). When tested in Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) - IIRRI Collaborative Lowland Consortium Trials in eastern India during 1992, TCA48 significantly outyielded local checks under normal and delayed transplanting (Table 2). TCA48 was resistant to BS, BB, and sheath rot (ShR). In pest complex reaction trials at Pusa, TCA48 yields declined by only 5.0% in 1991-92 and 8.7% in 1992-93 relative to protected checks.

TCA48 was released as Vaidehi in 1993. Vaidehi is a photoperiod-sensitive variety with sturdy stems, dark green foliage, and long panicles. It is 140-150 cm tall. Grain is long and bold; the kernel is faintly red.

Vaidehi should be a stable performer in the presence of BS, ShR, and BB, and across a range of transplanting times and problem lowland and shallow deepwater conditions. ■

Table 1. Performance of TCA48 and checks Mahsuri and Br. 8 in state multilocal varietal trials in 20 environments. 1986-92.

Year	Site	Yield (t/ha)			LSD (5%)	CV (%)
		TCA48	Mahsuri	Br. 8		
1986	Patna	3.0	2.7	2.2	0.5	10.0
	Pusa	3.1	2.9	1.9	0.6	12.6
	Sabour	2.9	3.0	3.0	0.7	14.4
1987	Patna	1.8	1.9	1.4	0.8	24.0
	Sabour	3.8	3.4	2.6	0.6	16.8
	Bikramganj	2.6	4.1	2.2	0.4	9.0
1988	Patna	3.8	3.7	2.4	1.0	16.4
	Sabour	3.3	3.2	2.0	0.5	14.2
	Bikramganj	4.4	3.8	2.7	0.7	10.6
1989	Patna	4.1	2.0	1.9	0.8	20.7
	Pusa	3.2	2.0	2.3	1.2	9.8
	Sabour	2.7	2.6	2.6	0.4	8.6
	Bikramganj	3.6	3.6	2.5	0.7	14.8
1990	Pusa	3.1	2.3	2.2	0.7	20.0
	Sabour	3.0	2.6	2.6	0.5	10.3
1991	Patna	2.9	2.8	2.5	1.2	23.0
	Sabour	2.1	2.7	3.0	0.2	5.5
1992	Patna	4.0	2.5	3.4	1.0	18.5
	Pusa	1.0	0.2	0.5	0.6	46.5
	Sabour	2.2	2.5	2.2	0.4	12.8
Pooled mean		3.0	2.7	2.3	0.7	-
Pooled LSD (0.05)		0.6	0.6	0.4	-	-

Table 2. Performance of TCA48 in different sites in eastern India under ICAR-IIRRI Collaborative Lowland Consortium Trials. 1992 kharif.

Site	Transplanting	Yield (t/ha)		LSD (5%)	CV (%)
		TCA48	Check		
Pusa	Normal	4.0	2.3	0.5	15.7
	Delayed	2.7	2.0	0.4	15.1
Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack	Normal	2.4	0.7	0.6	17.7
	Delayed	2.7	1.5	0.8	17.8
Masodha	Normal	3.5	1.8	1.0	29.0
	Delayed	-	-	-	-
Pooled mean		3.3	2.7		
Pooled LSD (0.05)		0.7	0.6		